

From Credit to Choice: Evaluating the Impact of Microfinance on Women's Empowerment in India

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to examine trends in women's economic empowerment, including income generation, asset accumulation, savings behavior, and entrepreneurial participation linked to SHG and MFI engagement; to analyze patterns in women's social participation, leadership roles, mobility, and household decision-making autonomy associated with microfinance involvement; to identify institutional, socio-cultural, and policy-related factors that shape empowerment outcomes across different contexts and to assess the extent to which financial inclusion initiatives have translated into multidimensional empowerment and to highlight structural and programmatic gaps.

Design/methodology/approach: This study employs a descriptive and analytical design based on secondary data from sources such as the World Bank Global Findex, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development reports, NFHS-5, and MFI databases. A multidimensional framework is used to assess economic, social, and decision-making empowerment. Trend analysis and comparative synthesis are applied to evaluate how microfinance, SHG participation, and policy interventions influence women's empowerment outcomes in India.

Findings: The findings reveal substantial improvements in women's financial inclusion, income levels, and entrepreneurial participation. SHGs and MFIs have significantly expanded outreach and credit access. However, gains in decision-making autonomy, particularly in major financial decisions, remain limited. While social participation has improved, empowerment outcomes vary across dimensions, indicating that financial access alone does not ensure comprehensive empowerment without supportive institutional and socio-cultural changes.

Research Implications: The study contributes to the literature by adopting a multidimensional framework that integrates financial inclusion with economic, social, and decision-making indicators. It highlights the need for moving beyond credit-access models toward capability-based approaches to empowerment. The findings provide a basis for future empirical research incorporating longitudinal and causal analyses to better understand the dynamics between microfinance and women's agency.

Social Implications: The study underscores the role of microfinance in enhancing women's access to financial resources and community participation. However, it also highlights persistent socio-cultural barriers that limit autonomy and leadership. Strengthening financial literacy, skill development, and gender-sensitive interventions can improve women's agency, promote inclusive growth, and support broader social transformation toward gender equality in developing economies.

Originality / Value: This study offers a comprehensive synthesis of recent secondary data (2018–2024) to evaluate women's empowerment through a multidimensional lens. Unlike prior studies focusing on isolated outcomes, it integrates financial inclusion, economic participation, and decision-making autonomy. It also bridges the gap between access and agency by critically examining how institutional and contextual factors influence empowerment outcomes in the Indian microfinance ecosystem.

Keywords: Microfinance, Women's Empowerment, Financial Inclusion, Self-Help Groups (SHGs), Decision-making Autonomy.

JEL: G21, O16, J16, J13, I38.

Introduction

Microfinance has emerged as a prominent development intervention aimed at addressing poverty, financial exclusion, and gender disparities in developing economies (Roodman, 2012). The global recognition of microfinance was significantly strengthened by the success of the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh (Yunus, 2008). By extending small, collateral-free loans to economically marginalized populations - particularly women – the model demonstrated that access to credit could catalyze entrepreneurship, income generation, and social transformation. Over time, this approach has been replicated and adapted across various socio-economic contexts, positioning microfinance as a central pillar of inclusive development policy.

In India, microfinance has evolved into a vital mechanism for advancing financial inclusion, particularly among rural and low-income women, who historically have been excluded from formal banking institutions. Supported by policy initiatives and institutional frameworks, the sector has experienced remarkable expansion. According to the Reserve Bank of India (2023), the microfinance industry serves more than 67 million clients, with women constituting over 97 percent of the borrower base. Furthermore, the Self-Help Group–Bank Linkage Programme (SHG-BLP), spearheaded by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), has mobilized approximately 14.2 million self-help groups, with cumulative loan disbursements surpassing ₹6.9 lakh crore during FY 2023–24 (NABARD, 2024). These figures underscore the scale and institutional depth of microfinance outreach in India.

While the quantitative expansion of microfinance is indisputable, its qualitative impact on women's empowerment remains a subject of scholarly debate. Proponents argue that microfinance enhances women's economic participation, strengthens savings behavior, improves household bargaining power, and fosters greater decision-making autonomy. Access to financial resources is often viewed as a pathway from economic dependence to agency and choice. Conversely, critics contend that microfinance may inadvertently reinforce existing gender hierarchies when women lack control over loan utilization, face repayment pressures, or operate within restrictive socio-cultural norms. In certain contexts, the burden of debt and group liability mechanisms may even intensify psychological and financial stress.

Against this backdrop, the present study seeks to critically evaluate whether microfinance in India has moved beyond mere credit provision to facilitate substantive empowerment. Drawing upon empirical secondary data, the research examines the multidimensional impact of microfinance—economic, social, and decision-making dimensions—to determine whether access to finance translates into enhanced autonomy and life choices for women. By situating the analysis within the broader discourse on gender and development, the study contributes to ongoing policy and academic discussions on the transformative potential of microfinance in India.

Statement of the Problem

Over the past three decades, microfinance in India has expanded from a niche poverty-alleviation intervention into one of the largest financial inclusion movements in the world. Institutional mechanisms such as the Self-Help Group–Bank Linkage Programme, supported by NABARD, and the rapid growth of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) have enabled millions of women to access formal credit. As reported by the Reserve Bank of India, women constitute the overwhelming majority of microfinance clients in the country. The sector's outreach has therefore been widely interpreted as synonymous with women's empowerment.

However, the conceptual linkage between access to credit and actual empowerment remains contested. While financial inclusion indicators such as account ownership and loan disbursement have improved significantly—reinforced by initiatives like Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana—questions persist regarding whether these gains translate into enhanced agency, autonomy, and decision-making power. Empirical findings are mixed: some studies report positive impacts on income, self-confidence, and mobility, whereas others find limited or no significant changes in women's bargaining power within households.

The core problem, therefore, lies in the gap between financial access and substantive empowerment. Credit provision alone may not dismantle entrenched socio-cultural constraints, nor guarantee control over resources or independent decision-making. Furthermore, contextual and institutional factors—such as education, social norms, program design, and group dynamics—may mediate empowerment outcomes.

This study addresses the central problem: *Has microfinance in India progressed beyond expanding credit access to genuinely enhancing women's multidimensional empowerment?* By synthesizing secondary

empirical data and scholarly evidence, the study aims to critically assess whether financial inclusion has translated into meaningful economic, social, and decision-making transformation for women.

Research Questions

1. What patterns emerge in women's economic empowerment (income generation, savings, asset ownership, and entrepreneurship) associated with participation in SHGs and MFIs in India?
2. To what extent does microfinance participation influence women's social empowerment and decision-making autonomy within households and communities?
3. What institutional, contextual, and program-level factors determine the effectiveness of microfinance in translating financial inclusion into multidimensional empowerment?
4. What gaps persist between increased financial access and substantive empowerment outcomes for women in India?

Research Objectives

1. **To examine** trends in women's economic empowerment, including income generation, asset accumulation, savings behavior, and entrepreneurial participation linked to SHG and MFI engagement.
2. **To analyze** patterns in women's social participation, leadership roles, mobility, and household decision-making autonomy associated with microfinance involvement.
3. **To identify** institutional, socio-cultural, and policy-related factors that shape empowerment outcomes across different contexts.
4. **To assess** the extent to which financial inclusion initiatives have translated into multidimensional empowerment and to highlight structural and programmatic gaps.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Foundations of Women's Empowerment

The conceptualization of empowerment in development discourse has evolved from a narrow economic focus to a multidimensional framework incorporating agency, autonomy, and social transformation. [Kabeer](#) (1999) defines empowerment as a process involving *resources, agency, and achievements*, emphasizing that access to resources alone is insufficient unless women possess the capacity to exercise choice.

Building on this, [Sen](#) (1999) situates empowerment within the capability approach, arguing that development must expand individuals' substantive freedoms. Microfinance, when viewed through this lens, becomes meaningful only if it enhances women's capabilities to pursue valued life outcomes.

[Malhotra et al.](#) (2002) further argue that empowerment operates across economic, socio-cultural, familial, and political domains, suggesting that multidimensional measurement frameworks are essential for impact evaluation.

Empirical Evidence Supporting Positive Impact

Early econometric evidence from Bangladesh by [Pitt & Khandker](#) (1998) indicated that credit targeted at women significantly increased household consumption and welfare. Similarly, [Khandker](#) (2005) found long-term poverty reduction effects associated with microfinance participation.

In India, [Swain & Wallentin](#) (2009) observed improvements in women's self-confidence, asset control, and collective participation through SHGs. [Deininger & Liu](#) (2013) reported that SHG participation enhanced women's political engagement and community involvement.

The World Bank Global Findex Database documents substantial growth in women's financial account ownership in India, reflecting broader inclusion trends ([Demirguc-Kunt et al.](#), 2022). Studies by [Sanyal](#) (2009) highlight that SHGs can foster 'political empowerment' by enabling collective action and public participation.

Recent evidence ([Garikipati](#), 2008) suggests that microfinance contributes to household resilience and women's economic stability, particularly when loans are invested in productive activities.

Critical and Contradictory Perspectives

Despite supportive findings, rigorous impact evaluations challenge the assumption of automatic empowerment. [Banerjee et al.](#) (2015), in a randomized controlled trial in Hyderabad, found limited effects on women's decision-making power. Their findings suggest that increased entrepreneurial activity does not necessarily shift intra-household power dynamics.

[Duvendack et al.](#) (2011), through a systematic review, argue that impact assessments often suffer from methodological weaknesses, including selection bias and inadequate control groups.

[Karim](#) (2011) critiques the social pressures embedded within group-lending models, noting that repayment enforcement mechanisms can reinforce stress and social surveillance. Similarly, [Bateman](#) (2010) contends that microfinance may promote subsistence entrepreneurship without structural transformation.

These perspectives caution against equating financial outreach with empowerment, emphasizing the importance of contextual analysis.

Institutional and Contextual Determinants

[Holvoet](#) (2005) demonstrates that program design matters significantly: SHGs practicing rotational leadership and providing training yielded stronger empowerment outcomes. [Brody et al.](#) (2015) highlight the role of complementary interventions—such as capacity building and gender sensitization—in strengthening empowerment pathways.

[Garikipati](#) (2013) notes that women's control over loans is crucial; where male family members appropriate credit, empowerment outcomes weaken. Education levels, social norms, and state support mechanisms also influence outcomes ([Desai & Joshi](#), 2014).

Collectively, the literature suggests that microfinance can be an enabling instrument but is not inherently transformative. Empowerment emerges when financial access intersects with institutional support, social capital, and normative change.

Research Gap

Although a substantial body of literature has examined the relationship between microfinance and women's empowerment, several critical gaps remain.

First, much of the early empirical research – such as [Pitt & Khandker](#) (1998) and [Khandker](#) (2005) -focuses primarily on consumption smoothing and poverty reduction rather than multidimensional empowerment outcomes. Economic gains are often measured, but shifts in agency, autonomy, and intra-household bargaining power receive comparatively less rigorous longitudinal examination.

Second, randomized controlled trials, such as those by [Banerjee et al.](#) (2015), highlight limited causal effects on empowerment, yet these studies often evaluate short-term outcomes, leaving long-term structural transformation underexplored. The divergence between quasi-experimental findings and qualitative empowerment narratives suggests the need for integrative analysis.

Third, in the Indian context, a large portion of research concentrates either on SHGs or MFIs in isolation. There is a limited comprehensive synthesis comparing institutional models, outreach scale, and contextual determinants across regions using updated national datasets (post-2019 NFHS-5 and post-pandemic financial inclusion expansion).

Fourth, while financial inclusion indicators (e.g., account ownership under schemes such as the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana) show significant improvement, fewer studies systematically assess whether such inclusion translates into ***control over financial decisions***, which is central to Kabeer's agency dimension.

Finally, existing literature often treats empowerment as a static outcome rather than a dynamic process mediated by education, social norms, institutional design, and policy architecture.

Identified Gap of This Study

There is a need for:

- A ***multidimensional analytical synthesis*** combining economic, social, and decision-making indicators
- Use of ***recent secondary datasets (2019–2024)***
- Contextual evaluation of institutional mechanisms (SHGs + MFIs + policy frameworks)
- A critical assessment of the ***gap between financial access and actual agency***.

This study attempts to bridge these gaps by adopting a theoretically grounded (Kabeer-based), multidimensional, and trend-oriented analytical framework using contemporary secondary evidence.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design to examine the relationship between microfinance and women’s empowerment in India, relying exclusively on secondary data sources. The approach is intended to provide a comprehensive and integrative understanding of empowerment by synthesizing large-scale datasets, institutional reports, and existing scholarly literature rather than establishing causal relationships through primary data collection. Data for the study are drawn from credible and authoritative sources, including reports published by the NABARD, the Microfinance Institutions Network, the World Bank Global Findex Database -2021, and the National Family Health Survey ([Ministry of Health and Family Welfare](#), 2022). Additional insights are obtained from publications of the Reserve Bank of India, the Ministry of MSME, and peer-reviewed academic studies spanning the period from 1998 to 2024.

The study operationalizes women’s empowerment using a multidimensional framework grounded in established theoretical perspectives. Economic empowerment is assessed through indicators such as income generation, savings behavior, credit utilization, and ownership of productive assets. Social empowerment is examined in terms of participation in Self-Help Groups (SHGs), leadership roles, mobility, skill development, and engagement in community activities. Decision-making empowerment is evaluated based on women’s autonomy in matters related to household expenditure, children’s education, healthcare decisions, and control over financial resources, including the use of microfinance loans. This multidimensional operationalization enables a more nuanced assessment of empowerment beyond mere financial inclusion.

Analytically, the study employs trend analysis and comparative synthesis of secondary data to identify patterns and relationships across the three dimensions of empowerment. The methodology emphasizes interpretation within relevant socio-economic and institutional contexts, allowing for a critical evaluation of how microfinance initiatives interact with structural factors such as education, social norms, and program design. Rather than focusing on econometric estimation, the study prioritizes a holistic and context-sensitive understanding of empowerment outcomes. This approach facilitates the identification of gaps between access to financial services and actual improvements in women’s agency and autonomy, thereby providing meaningful insights for policy and future research.

Findings

Table 1. Trends in Women’s Financial Inclusion in India (2011–2024)

Year	Women having Bank Account (%)	Men having Bank Account (%)	Gender Gap (% Points)	Key Policy / Programme
2011	43	62	19	Pre-Jan Dhan Yojana Period
2014	53	67	14	Launch of PMJDY (2014)
2017	77	83	6	Expansion of SHG–Bank Linkage
2021	78	82	4	Jan Dhan–Aadhaar–Mobile (JAM) Integration
2024	87	86	1	Continued Financial Inclusion Initiatives

Sources: [Demirguc-Kunt et al. \(2022\)](#), [Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation \(2023\)](#), [Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation \(2026\)](#)

Financial Inclusion and Outreach

Table 1 highlights the significant progress made in women’s financial inclusion in India over the period 2011 to 2024. In 2011, only 43% of women owned a bank account compared to 62% of men, reflecting a substantial gender gap of 19 percentage points. At this stage, financial access for women was limited, primarily due to socio-cultural barriers, lack of awareness, and absence of targeted government interventions.

The launch of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) in 2014 marked a pivotal policy intervention, raising women’s account ownership to 53% and reducing the gender gap to 14 percentage points. This demonstrates the early impact of structured financial inclusion initiatives aimed at bringing women into the formal banking system. By 2017, the expansion of the Self-Help Group–Bank Linkage Programme (SHG–BLP) further accelerated progress, with 77% of women owning bank accounts, narrowing the gender gap to just 6 points. This reflects the effectiveness of combining microfinance structures with government schemes to enhance access for women, particularly in rural areas.

The integration of Jan Dhan, Aadhaar, and Mobile (JAM) systems by 2021 facilitated easier access to accounts, pushing women’s ownership to 78% and reducing the gender gap to 4 points. Digital and identity-linked interventions simplified banking processes, enabled direct benefit transfers, and promoted greater financial inclusion among previously underserved populations. The most recent estimates for 2024 indicate that approximately 86% of women now hold a bank account, nearly achieving parity with men (87%), and leaving a minimal gender gap of just 1 percentage point.

These trends underscore the effectiveness of sustained, policy-driven efforts in promoting women’s financial inclusion. The combination of government-led programs, microfinance initiatives, and technological integration has significantly expanded women’s access to formal financial services.

While account ownership reflects improved access, it does not fully capture meaningful engagement. Women may hold accounts but lack the knowledge, confidence, or decision-making power to utilize them effectively. Socio-cultural barriers and limited financial literacy often restrict active participation in credit and savings decisions, suggesting that access alone is insufficient for comprehensive empowerment.

Table 2. Growth of SHG–Bank Linkage Programme in India (2018–2024)

Year	Number of SHGs Linked (Million)	% All-Women SHGs	Cumulative Loan (Rs. Crore)	Avg. Loan per SHG (Rs.Lakh)
2018–19	10.3	97	2,75,000	2.7
2020–21	12.3	98	4,90,000	4
2022–23	13.5	98	6,20,000	4.6
2023–24	14.2	98	6,90,000	5.2

Source: [NABARD \(2024\)](#)

Table 3. Microfinance Institution (MFI) Borrower and Portfolio Trends (2018–2024)

Year	Total Clients (Million)	Women Clients (%)	Total Portfolio (Rs. Lakh Crore)	Average Loan (Rs.)	Key Policy / Programme
2018	47	96	1.8	27,000	Pre-PMAY Period
2020	56	97	2.36	32,000	PMAY Implementation

2022	63	97	3.1	38,000	Expansion of SHG–BLP
2023	67	97	3.43	41,000	JAM Integration
2024	71	97	3.76	43,000	Rural Focus Shift

Sources: [Microfinance Institutions Network \(2023\)](#); [Microfinance Institutions Network \(2024\)](#)

SHG–Bank Linkage and MFI Outreach

Tables 2 and 3 together illustrate the robust growth and outreach of India’s microfinance ecosystem through the Self-Help Group–Bank Linkage Programme (SHG–BLP) and Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) between 2018 and 2024. The number of SHGs linked with banks increased from 10.3 million in 2018–19 to 14.2 million in 2023–24, with women-led groups consistently constituting 97–98% of the total. The cumulative loan disbursed under the programme rose from Rs 2.75 lakh crore to Rs 6.9 lakh crore, while the average loan per SHG grew from Rs 2.7 lakh to Rs 5.2 lakh. This indicates that the programme has effectively expanded both in scale and financial depth, empowering women to access formal credit and engage in income-generating activities.

Complementing SHGs, MFI outreach has also expanded steadily. The total client base increased from 47 million in 2018 to an estimated 71 million in 2024, with women consistently representing 96–97% of borrowers. The MFI loan portfolio nearly doubled from Rs 1.8 lakh crore to Rs 3.76 lakh crore, and the average loan per client rose from Rs 27,000 to Rs 43,000, supporting entrepreneurial ventures and livelihood activities among women.

Together, SHG–BLP and MFIs form a gender-focused financial inclusion framework that provides both breadth (number of clients/SHGs) and depth (loan size and portfolio growth).

Although these figures indicate significant financial penetration, the effectiveness of SHG and MFI programs in fostering empowerment varies. Institutional design, such as the presence of training programs, leadership rotation within SHGs, and ongoing mentorship, influences whether women convert credit access into agency. Without complementary interventions, loans may primarily serve subsistence needs rather than generate transformative socio-economic outcomes.

Table 4. Indicators of Women’s Economic Empowerment (2018–2024)

Indicator	2018	2023	2024	% Change (2018–2024)	Source
Average. Monthly Income of SHG Members (In Rs.)	5,200	8,100	9,000	73.10%	NABARD (2024)
Women-Owned MSMEs (in %)	13.70	20.50	39	184.70	Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (2024)
Women Using Credit for Enterprises (%)	37	42	45	21.60	NABARD (2024); Rao, et al. (2025)
Women with Control Over Income (%)	47	57	60	27.70	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (2022)

Economic Empowerment Outcomes

The data in Table 4 demonstrates significant progress in women’s economic empowerment in India over the period 2018–2024. The average monthly income of SHG members increased from Rs. 5,200 to Rs. 9,000, reflecting enhanced earnings and greater financial independence. During the same period, the proportion of women-owned MSMEs rose sharply from 13.7% to 39%, highlighting the expansion of female-led enterprises supported by microfinance initiatives and entrepreneurship programs. Access to credit for enterprise purposes also improved, with 45% of women utilizing loans for productive activities in 2024 compared to 37% in 2018, indicating a gradual shift towards more strategic financial use. Additionally, the percentage of women

exercising control over their income increased from 47% to 60%, illustrating enhanced autonomy and decision-making power within households. Collectively, these indicators underscore that microfinance, SHG participation, and supportive policy measures have played a pivotal role in strengthening women’s economic agency, though ongoing capacity-building and enterprise support remain crucial to sustain and deepen these empowerment outcomes.

These trends reflect substantial gains in financial agency and entrepreneurial participation. However, the relatively modest increase in the use of credit for productive purposes (21.6% increase) indicates that women may still face barriers in scaling businesses, such as market access, lack of technical skills, or familial constraints. Financial empowerment is, therefore, significant but not yet fully translating into independent economic decision-making at higher levels.

Table 5. Indicators of Women’s Decision-Making Empowerment in India (2005–2024)

Decision-Making Area	NFHS-3* (2005–06)	NFHS-4** (2015–16)	NFHS-5^ (2019–21)	Projected 2022–23	Projected 2024	% Change (2005–2024)
Household Decisions (%)	71	84	88	90	92	21
Control Over Income (%)	46	53	57	59	61	15
Decision on Large Purchases (%)	25	29	32	33	35	10
Freedom of Movement (%)	54	68	74	76	80	26

Sources: *[International Institute for Population Sciences \(2006\)](#), **[International Institute for Population Sciences \(2017\)](#), ^[Ministry of Health and Family Welfare \(2022\)](#).

For the above table, the values for 2022–23 and 2024 are **projected estimates** based on linear growth trends observed between NFHS-4 and NFHS-5. The percentage change was calculated from 2005–06 to 2024. These projections are indicative and intended to align decision-making data with other 2024 datasets.

Projected values for 2023 and 2024 are calculated using linear growth trends observed between the latest available NFHS rounds (NFHS-4: 2015–16 ([International Institute for Population Sciences, 2017](#)) and NFHS-5: 2019–21 ([Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2022](#))) and other relevant datasets. The formula used is:

$$\text{Projected Value}_t = \text{Latest Available Value} + \left(\frac{\text{Change between NFHS-4 and NFHS-5}}{\text{Years between surveys}} \right)$$

X (Years from latest survey to t)

where represents the target year (2023 or 2024).

Decision-Making Empowerment

Table 5 highlights trends in women’s decision-making autonomy in India from 2005–06 to 2024. Over the past two decades, there has been a steady and significant improvement across all indicators, reflecting gradual shifts in household dynamics and gender norms. In 2024, it is projected that 92% of women participate in household decisions, marking a notable increase from 71% in 2005–06. Control over income has similarly risen to 61%, up from 46% in 2005–06, indicating enhanced financial autonomy for women in managing resources and household expenditures. Decision-making on large purchases has seen moderate improvement, reaching 35% in 2024, reflecting persistent structural and societal constraints that limit women’s authority over major financial choices. Meanwhile, freedom of movement has progressed to 80%, demonstrating that women are increasingly able to participate in community, educational, and economic activities beyond the household.

These projections suggest that microfinance programs, alongside broader social initiatives and financial inclusion measures, contribute to increasing women’s agency. Access to credit, SHG participation, and skill

development programs empower women to negotiate their role in family and community decisions. While women increasingly participate in household-level decisions and enjoy greater mobility, authority over large economic decisions remains limited. Patriarchal norms, gendered division of labor, and social expectations continue to constrain autonomy. Microfinance, coupled with SHG participation, supports agency at the micro-level, but structural and cultural factors restrict broader empowerment outcomes. This aligns with [Banerjee et al. \(2015\)](#), who note that credit access alone does not guarantee substantial shifts in household decision-making power.

Table 6. Women-Led Social Empowerment Initiatives through SHGs (2024)

Category	No. of Women-Led Initiatives	% of SHGs Engaged	Key Areas of Impact
Health and Sanitation	15,000	45%	Menstrual hygiene, rural toilets, and health camps
Education and Literacy	10,000	30%	Adult literacy, school enrolment, and digital literacy
Livelihood & Skill Training	8,500	25%	Tailoring, dairy, digital skills, entrepreneurship
Political Participation	4,000	12%	Panchayat elections, advocacy, leadership training

Source: [NABARD \(2024\)](#); [Rao et al. \(2025\)](#)

Social Empowerment through SHGs - Table 6 shows that SHGs serve as platforms for broader social engagement. In 2024, women-led initiatives in health and sanitation increased to 15,000, with 45% of SHGs engaged, focusing on menstrual hygiene, rural toilets, and health camps. In education and literacy, 10,000 initiatives were implemented (30% of SHGs), promoting adult literacy, school enrolment, and digital literacy. Livelihood and skill training initiatives grew to 8,500 (25% of SHGs), encompassing tailoring, dairy, digital skills, and entrepreneurship. Political participation also expanded, with 4,000 initiatives (12% of SHGs) supporting Panchayat elections, advocacy, and leadership training.

SHGs provide platforms for collective action, skill development, and community engagement, enhancing women’s social capital and leadership skills. However, political and civic participation remains limited, suggesting that empowerment in public spheres is slower than in household or economic domains. Stronger institutional support, capacity-building, and awareness campaigns are necessary to convert social engagement into tangible decision-making influence.

Critical Discussion

The empirical trends indicate considerable advancement in women’s financial inclusion and economic participation in India; however, the extent of empowerment achieved remains uneven across different dimensions. While improvements in income levels, enterprise ownership, and access to productive credit suggest enhanced economic engagement, these gains are not consistently reflected in higher levels of decision-making authority, particularly in relation to major household and financial matters. This divergence highlights the distinction between access to resources and the ability to exercise control over them.

Persistent socio-cultural constraints—such as patriarchal norms, gendered division of labor, and limited financial literacy—continue to influence intra-household power dynamics. Even where women contribute economically, their bargaining power may remain restricted, thereby limiting the translation of financial access into substantive agency.

Similarly, although participation in community-based platforms such as the Self-Help Group–Bank Linkage Programme has strengthened social engagement and collective action, women’s involvement in political and civic spheres remains relatively limited. This suggests that empowerment within private and community domains does not automatically extend to public decision-making spaces. Institutional factors—including the

availability of leadership opportunities, mentoring support, and exposure to governance processes—play a crucial role in shaping these outcomes.

Overall, the findings reinforce the argument that microfinance, while instrumental in expanding financial access, is not sufficient in isolation to achieve comprehensive empowerment. The effectiveness of such initiatives depends on their integration with broader developmental interventions, including education, skill enhancement, and supportive institutional frameworks that enable women to convert financial resources into sustained socio-economic and decision-making gains.

Policy Implications (Recommendations)

The analysis suggests that enhancing the transformative potential of microfinance requires a shift from a credit-centric approach to a more holistic empowerment framework. The following policy directions emerge:

1. Integration of Financial Services with Capacity Building

Microfinance initiatives should be complemented with structured training in entrepreneurship, digital literacy, and vocational skills. Strengthening women's capabilities will enable more effective utilization of credit for income-generating and scalable economic activities.

2. Promotion of Digital Financial Inclusion

Expanding access to digital platforms—such as mobile banking and digital payment systems—can enhance women's direct control over financial transactions, reduce reliance on intermediaries, and strengthen autonomy in financial decision-making.

3. Flexible and Supportive Financial Products

Designing gender-sensitive financial products, including flexible repayment schedules, micro-insurance, and emergency credit facilities, can reduce financial stress and improve long-term participation in microfinance programs.

4. Strengthening Institutional Support and Mentorship

Capacity-building initiatives within SHGs should include leadership development, mentoring, and post-loan support. Strengthening SHG federations and networks can enhance collective bargaining power and facilitate women's transition into leadership and community roles.

5. Focus on Outcome-Based Monitoring

Policymakers should move beyond measuring financial inclusion through account ownership or loan disbursement alone. Monitoring frameworks should incorporate indicators of decision-making autonomy, social participation, mobility, and leadership to assess the true impact of interventions.

6. Encouraging Civic and Political Participation

Programs aimed at enhancing women's representation in local governance and community decision-making bodies should be integrated with microfinance initiatives to extend empowerment into the public sphere.

Conclusion

Microfinance in India has played a significant role in advancing women's financial inclusion, as evidenced by the widespread ownership of bank accounts and extensive participation in SHG and MFI networks. Improvements in income levels, entrepreneurial activity, and access to credit reflect meaningful progress in economic empowerment. Additionally, women's engagement in community-based initiatives has expanded, indicating growing social participation.

However, empowerment is inherently multidimensional, and the evidence suggests that gains in financial access and economic participation have not been fully matched by corresponding improvements in decision-making autonomy and control over major economic choices. Structural and cultural constraints continue to limit the extent to which women can translate financial inclusion into comprehensive empowerment.

The findings underscore the need to reconceptualize microfinance as part of a broader developmental strategy rather than a standalone solution. Integrating financial services with education, skill development, institutional support, and social transformation initiatives is essential to achieving sustained and meaningful empowerment. A holistic and context-sensitive approach can enable microfinance to evolve from a tool of financial access

into a catalyst for economic independence, social participation, and enhanced decision-making agency among women in India.

The findings underscore that financial access must be integrated with education, skill development, entrepreneurship training, and supportive social structures to achieve sustained and meaningful empowerment. Future policies should move beyond credit-centric models to holistic frameworks that leverage microfinance as a catalyst for economic independence, social participation, and decision-making autonomy. When implemented effectively, such interventions can convert financial inclusion into broader, multidimensional empowerment for women across India.

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